

OVERVIEW OF NATIONAL AND GLOBAL SCENARIO OF CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRIES

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ABSTRACT:

By 2025, the contribution of construction industry in India's GDP is expected to be more than 10%. Better infrastructure is a sign of development of any country. Construction industries in the developed countries are not only working on infrastructure development but also to produce the international quality infrastructure. The GDP of the country is always supported to great extent by the construction industries. For the developing countries like India the scope for betterment of infrastructure is still a challenge to take. The current Indian government is focusing on the infrastructure development and improvement in technology. In this paper, author has tried presenting the national and global scenario of construction industries. Infrastructure development always plays a vital role in the economic development of the country. The infrastructure development is mainly carried out by construction industries. The challenge of today's construction industries is to utilize the technology in order to upgrade the quality of construction projects. Moreover, the construction industries contribute directly and indirectly as well for the development of country.

KEYWORDS: Construction industries, infrastructure development, construction technology, etc.

INTRODUCTION:

Fast development of the country is rated by the infrastructure development of the country. It was observed that the construction industries have played a vital role in the development of countries by contributing to the GDP of the respective country effectively.

Fig.2: GDP contribution of construction in China

Fig.3: GDP contribution of construction in US

Fig.4: GDP contribution of construction in UK

Fig.5: GDP contribution of construction in Russia

Fig.1: GDP contribution of construction in India

Fig.6: GDP contribution of construction in Malaysia

The growth of the nation is known with infrastructure and in the modern era of globalization, the centre of global attraction is developed infrastructure. The following figures are showing the contribution of construction industries in the GDP of different countries. With Increase in population there is need of huge infrastructure worldwide. In the countries like India, having own house is the symbol of success and having own business office is considered the symbol of status. This shows the will of Indian society to have the own home/ office. Due to this the construction business in India is growing continuously and rapidly.

LITERATURE SURVEY:

A.L. Olanrewaju and A.R. Abdul-Aziz et.al in chapter 2 of their book have presented the scenario of construction in Malaysia. In this chapter the scenario of construction from the point of view of infrastructural requirement of the education industry is presented. The correlation between the two is explained in detail. The problems related to Malaysian construction industries have been discussed for better understanding. The worldwide study proven that there is remarkable contribution of the construction industries in economic development of the nation and vice versa. People are having different opinions on this issue still [2].

Swarup, P. R. et.al has presented the practices in the Indian construction industries. The construction Industry is found one of the largest employers in India and worldwide. Various processes, management and contract forms are discussed in this paper. Various procedures of certification are also discussed. Authors have also included the social, political and legal issues related to construction. Authors have concluded that the growth of the construction industry will be supported by Indian conditions [3].

Rai, Shweta, and Prateek Ghavate et.al have briefed about the scenario and rise in construction industries. Being one of the fastest growing economies India has huge scope for infrastructure development and here the key role is played by the construction industries. Policy makers in India are always supporting the infra structure development plan in India. This supports construction industries to develop. Huge finance is one of the important requirements of this industry. The demand is continuously increasing with time and it is creating opportunities for the employment too [4].

Gann, David, and Peter Senker et.al have proposed that the skill development in the construction industry is most needed. Authors have discussed about the scenario of construction industries in UK. The improvement in the performance of any construction industry needs the trained workers and people on key positions. Use of new technologies is mandatory. The analysis made to make the decisions by the policy makers of UK to upgrade the level of training in order to improve the quality of the construction projects their by enhancing skills of workers [5].

Khakee, Abdul et.al has presented the literature on urban planning from the point of view of construction projects. The brief discussion on the urban planning problems is covered in this paper. Few of important issues related to construction scenario are also discussed in details. Proper planning of the construction project is necessary in order to enhance the quality of projects [6].

CONCLUSION:

Authors have presented the review of construction industries scenario in this paper. Presently, the construction industries are continuously growing and it has the potential to serve even more to the GDP of various countries. The construction industries are mainly facing the problems like less available skilled staff, lack of implementation technology and rigidity to stick to the conventional methods. In India construction industries and associated businesses are second largest in providing the employment.

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